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**NATIONAL AND ETHIC WORLD MAPPING THROUGH
DECOLONIZING LITERARY METHODOLOGY**

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Oksana Shostak. National and Ethic world mapping through decolonizing literary methodology. The beginning of the twenty-first century is marked by a shift in the approach to understanding works written by writers of indigenous origin. Literary critics began to pay more attention to highlighting the peculiarities of specific nations, which led to the emergence of “literary nationalism”. Researchers' attention has moved from identifying features of authenticity, hybridity, and intercultural influences to search of intellectual, cultural, political, and historical aspects. The article's author is convinced that in Indigenous criticism, the past and the present are practically indistinguishable; they actively coexist, becoming a “reflection” of the national consciousness of Indigenous nations. The influence of the past upon the Native Americans is still really present in the socio-cultural context of contemporary literary criticism, which is essentially a non-linear reception in the minds of modern generations, which creates a polemical and oppositional discourse.

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In 1999, Linda Tuhiwai Smith, a representative of the Maori people from Australia, published her book “*Decolonizing Methodology. Research and Indigenous Peoples*”, which severely criticized the research methods of European science and culture in the study of indigenous cultures around the world. The book begins with a shocking statement

for any scholar: “From the perspective of the colonized person, the term ‘research’ is inextricably linked to European imperialism and colonialism. The word ‘research’ is probably the dirtiest in the vocabulary of all indigenous peoples of the world. Mentioned in the context of an Indigenous community, it causes a heavy silence, evokes bad memories and a wry smile.” (Smith, 2012, p. 1). Smith criticizes the Western paradigm of conducting research from the perspective of colonized peoples worldwide. The book denies the absoluteness of Western knowledge and research and calls for the “decolonization” of the methodology of researching the cultures of colonized peoples. “We are annoyed that Western researchers think they know everything about us after talking to a few of us. We are horrified by how easily the West extracts and appropriates our knowledge, our imagery, and the things we have created, rejecting the value of human life tied to the land and territories, their natural resources, denying the right to self-acknowledgment, ignoring their language and cultural characteristics.” (Smith, 2012, p. 5). Smith insists on the need for the researchers’ ethnocentric focus. Unfortunately, in the current scientific paradigm, anything related to indigenous peoples has the right to exist only if it fits into the general scheme of Western science and is of value to the dominant society. “Research is one of how the code of imperialism and colonialism is reinforced, regulated, and implemented. This code is governed by the formal rules and scientific paradigms of the discipline that each particular researcher studies, as state-funded academic institutions implement them. It is implemented through myriads of ideological constructions of the Other, which are replicated on the pages of scientific and popular books” (Smith, 2012, p. 11).

The author writes about the restrictions imposed by the Western paradigm on Indigenous scholars through specific methodologies inherent in the Western European worldview, which is actively imposed by the education system. “Many Indigenous researchers have had to struggle with the inconsistencies that have arisen between the requirements for research and the reality they face as part of an Indigenous community. There are ethical, cultural, political, and personal issues that can pose challenges for indigenous researchers who work in their communities as insiders, which is why they

were hired, but also as outsiders because of their Western education, and because of constraints related to clan, tribal, linguistic, age, or gender boundaries” (Smith, 2012, p. 5). The author writes about the resistance that occurs in contemporary Indigenous communities to research that affects the interests of Indigenous peoples. “In the context of contemporary indigenous studies, questions arise that are actively discussed. <...> Whose research is this? Who owns it? Whose interests does it serve? Who will benefit from it? Who formulated the range of issues under consideration? Who will conduct and document it? How will the knowledge gained from the research be disseminated?” (Smith, 2012, p. 10).

Smith emphasizes the limitations offered by Western education and the humiliation of the indigenous worldview in academic studies. “The biggest criticism and resentment among indigenous intellectuals and activists is that Western education does not allow us to write or speak from a ‘real’ authentic indigenous perspective. Those who defend the traditional indigenous point of view are criticised because what they say ‘doesn't make sense’ (speak English or something!). What we say is reduced to a ‘nativist’ discourse that academic colleagues simply do not take seriously, considering it naive, contradictory or lacking in logic” (Smith, 2012, p. 14). That is why, as the researcher explains, indigenous representatives of the academic community refuse to participate in any manifestations of postcolonial discourse, as they consider it “a convenient invention of Western intellectuals who use it to assert their right to define everything in the world” (Smith, 2012, p. 14).

Postcolonial discussions provoke resistance “not so much because of a new attempt to create a literary image of a culture that was once part of the colonial margins, but because of an attempt to introduce the idea that colonialism is already over. Indigenous scholars have every reason to suspect that the fashion for post-colonialism is a strategy to restore and reclaim the authority of non-indigenous scholars, as post-colonial discourse is defined in such a way as to exclude people of indigenous origin, our worldview, and our contemporary concerns” (Smith, 2012, p. 25).

The book *Decolonising Methodology* had a huge impact on the development of literary criticism in North America, provoking an active discussion about the role and place of literary critics of non-indigenous descent in analyzing the works of authors who are of Native American or First Nations of Canada descent. As a response to Smith's new perspective on indigenous studies, the following year the anthology *Skins: Contemporary Indigenous Writings* (2000), edited by Katherine Akiwenzi-Damm, a Chippewa from Canada, and Josie Douglas, a Wardaman from Australia, was published, featuring literary works from both First Nations of Canada and the United States, as well as writers from Australia and New Zealand. The book was published simultaneously in Canada and Australia. In the preface, Akiwenzi-Damm writes that there is still an attitude towards the work of indigenous peoples that she would describe as “intellectual and aesthetic apartheid”. “Our creativity, and there is a great deal of it, has thousands of years of existence, but racial segregation, silence, ignorance and neglect continue to be applied to it. All the authors of this collection share common traits, namely our attachment to our homeland, the history of genocide, colonisation and forced displacement, as well as the will to survive and the desire to pass on the pearls of our cultures to future generations” (Akiwenzie-Damm, 2000, p. 6).

In the same year, Sidney Larson's book *Captured in the Middle: Traditions and Experience in Contemporary Native American Writing* (2000) was published. The author proposes to involve additional scientific analysis that includes a dialogue between critics to avoid sole hegemony over the text. The researcher is concerned about the trends in Native American critical thought where critics accused each other of departing from the principles of “Indianness” and not adhering to the ideas born on the battlefields of the protest movements of the 60s and 70s. Larson calls for solving the problems of searching for national identity in critical studies by ending the hostilities that associate American Indians with the American Indian Movement. “There is no doubt that there are many reasons for massive nationalist political activity in the Indian world today. And I am grateful to those who have the courage to demand the return of what was stolen and to restore justice for the genocide against American Indians. Their good deeds allow me to

emphasise that there is something in common for representatives of different cultures” (Larson, 2000, p. 5).

In 2003, Robert Parker's *The Invention of Native American Literature* was published. In his research, the researcher addresses what should really be considered indigenous literature. He declares that he perceives the presence of this literature as a proper phenomenon of our time. He also insisted that Native American literature had aesthetic value, as well as Native American identity (Parker, 2003). He based his research on the works by Thomas King, John Matthews, Darcy McNickle, Leslie Marmon Silko, and Ray Young Bear. Parker tried to analyze the history of Native American literature by translating the ideas of oral literature into written text point of view, examining the peculiarities of the Native American masculinity embodiment in the analyzed texts, and the peculiarities of the attitude towards state institutions. Parker is sure that the desire to create indigenous literature has always brought Native American authors back to the paths of four specific themes. Namely, endangered youthful masculinity, oral culture, the peculiarities of Native American poetics, and the alienation of Native culture from what constitutes the values of mainstream culture (Parker, 2003). The particular interest in masculine manifestations in Native American literature was in opposition to P.G. Allen's feminist studies. Some of Parker's statements look like accusations. In his opinion, the heroes of Indian novels are sexually inactive, “they are always procrastinating, and if they do something, they do it without proper interest, which is a hint of latent homosexuality or, to put it less bluntly, it suggests their ambiguous sexuality. Their undefined, passive masculinity seems to be an unpleasant environment of Indian modernity and gender relations” (Parker, 2003, p. 5). The researcher is outraged by the tendency to underestimate the contribution of non-indigenous critics to the development of American Indian literature, and he didn't find Womack's arguments about essentialism convincing or well grounded in the debates that have been going on around this topic. Therefore, he disagreed with Womack's implicit thesis that non-indigenous critics have nothing substantive to offer when discussing indigenous literature (Parker, 2003). Parker explains the use of the word “invention” in the title of his book. He wanted to emphasize the

temporality and constant change in this process, which resists the natural and inevitable effusion of Indian identity. To view Indian art as such an effusion is to assume that Indian identity is extra-historical, static, and absolute, arrogantly created by others rather than constantly produced by Indians. According to Parker, without non-Indians, no one could imagine Indians as a category.

In 2007, Elizabeth Cooke-Lynn published an article entitled *New Indians, Old Wars*, in which she accused representatives of the contemporary Indigenous intellectual elite of passivity. In her opinion, while most scholars of Eastern descent, including the most prominent, she believes, the work of Edward Said, have searched for a solution to the negative effects of colonialism a priority, most Indian critics have been on the sidelines of this important process. She posed the question of what is really worth being at the center of Native American research. (Cooke-Lynn, 2007, p. 10). She argues that the history of the indigenous nations of North America is a useful expanding focus for finding the context of contemporary imperialist wars. “Nothing in the world happens without a preceding context, which is why the old Indian wars should be seen as the backdrop against which today's horrors unfold” (Cooke-Lynn, 2007, p. 72).

Cooke-Lynn cites the names of D'Arcy McNickle, before whom even the star of Wynne Deloria fades, as well as Greg Womack, as examples of true writers who do not deviate from their historical vocation. She calls the works of these writers “the strongest antidote” to the writing of most American Indians, who, in her opinion, continue to write the stories taught to them by their captors. The works of James Welch and Sherman Alexie received the most criticism for their depiction of the hopelessness of life on an Indian reservation. The researcher passionately demands that Native American writers and critics support the idea of a nationalist reading of texts, which, in her opinion, should support the idea of the struggle for sovereignty in the context of globalization.

In 2007, Duane Champagne published an article entitled *Search of Theory and Method in American Indian Studies*, where she writes that “the multidisciplinary approach to American Indian studies has improved somewhat over the past decade, but this has not significantly affected the conceptual approach that should define Indian Studies as a

discipline, developing its theoretical statements that would adequately present theoretical and methodological approaches to the study of indigenous peoples” (Champagne, 2007, p. 353). According to the researcher, the colonial and globalisation context creates new obstacles and opportunities for American Indian communities (Champagne, 2007). Champagne is convinced that theoretical thought is not keeping pace with the changes experienced by contemporary indigenous peoples of North America. In his article “*Go Away Water!*” *Kinship Criticism and the Decolonization Imperative*” (2008), Daniel Heath Justice argues that the most fruitful means for Indigenous criticism to employ is to be able to take into account the interconnections that connect the cultural, historical, political, and intellectual contexts from which each Indigenous text emerges. Such inclusiveness ensures a rich variety of interpretations and sensitizes the multiple connections and contexts that justify such research from a moral point of view (Justice, 2008, p. 165).

In 2008, an anthology of women's prose *Reckoning. Contemporary Short Fiction by Native American Women* was published, edited by Gerta Sweet Wong, Lauren Stuart Muller, and Gina Sequoia Magdaleno. In the preface to this edition, the compilers write that they chose the term “short fiction” rather than the more common short story” in American literature to denote the distinctiveness of the works written by the anthology's indigenous women authors. They stressed that the short story is a genre in the Euro-American literary tradition that creates a work with an opening, climax, and resolution in a sophisticated short form. Short fiction also belongs to the academically recognized literary genres, which includes the retelling of oral tales, narrative cycles, anecdotes, retelling of conversations, and stories that, as Leslie Silko illustrates, can be organized around the geographical context of the Pueblo people (Wong, 2008, p. 15). However, the compilers of the anthology later write that they do not seek to separate literary genres as purely Indian or vice versa. However, when describing the works included in the anthology, the researchers highlight the features characteristic of traditional indigenous oral narratives. The recurrent structural elements in the short fiction of this anthology include cyclical rather than linear narrative structures, layering of

multiple perspectives, emphasized geographically over temporality, translation of ordinary events into textual planes, destruction of the Western linearity of time (past and present exist simultaneously), depiction of the earth as a living being, interpenetration of myth and everyday life (Wong, 2008, p. 15). The compilers emphasized the principles by which the anthology was compiled: just as stories are passed down from one generation to the next, and in indigenous cultures it is customary to give the honor of speaking first to the elders, so the anthology has been built from the elders to the youngest.

In 2008, Weaver, Womack, and Warrior's resonant study *American Indian Literary Nationalism* was published. The authors examine the strengths and weaknesses of nationalism in literary works by writers of indigenous origin.

Summing up the above, it should be noted that in Native American criticism, the past and the present are practically indistinguishable; they actively coexist, becoming a “reflection” of the national consciousness of indigenous peoples. The influence of the past of the Indian nations is still really present in the socio-cultural context of contemporary literary criticism, which is essentially its non-linear reception in the minds of modern generations, which creates a polemical and oppositional discourse.

References:

- Akiwenzie-Damm, K. (2000). Preface: We remain, Forever// *Skins: Contemporary Indigenous Writing*/ Ed. by Kateri Akiwenzie-Damm and Josie Douglas. – Alice Spring, Australia : Jukurra Books, 2000, 6–9.
- Champagne, D. (2007). Search of Theory and Method in American Indian Studies. *American Indian Quarterly*, Vol. 31, No. 1, 353–372.
- Cook-Lynn, E. (2007). *New Indians, Old Wars*. Urbana : University of Illinois Press.
- Justice, D. H. (2008). “Go Away Water!” Kinship Criticism and the Decolonization Imperative. *Reasoning Together. The Native Critics Collective*. Ed. by Craig S. Womack, Daniel Heath Justice & Christopher B. Teuton. Norman : University of Oklahoma Press, 147–168.

- Larson, S. J. (2000). *Captured in the Middle: Traditions and Experiencing Contemporary Native American Writing*. Seattle : University of Washington Press.
- Parker, R. D. (2003). *The Invention of Native American Literature*. Ithaca, NY : Cornell University Press.
- Smith, L. T. (2012). *Decolonizing Methodologies: Research and Indigenous Peoples*. 2nd Edition. London : Zed.
- Weaver, J., Womack, G., & Warrior, R. A. (2006). *American Indian Literary Nationalism*. Albuquerque : University of New Mexico Press.
- Wong, H. D., Muller, L. S., & Magdaleno, J. S. (2008). Introduction. *Reckoning. Contemporary Short Fiction by Native American Women*. Oxford University Press, 13–19.